

ASSISTIVE TECHNOLOGY, DESIGN AND *GAMBIARRA*:

PERCEPTUAL NOTIONS OF DIFFERENT PENCIL THICKENERS THROUGH THE DS PROTOCOL

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ABSTRACT

This study intends to evaluate five models of a product of the assistive technology area, known as pencil grip, used for ergonomic adequacy, through an evaluation protocol called the Semantic Differential (SD). This object is widely used in rehabilitation environments, involving learning and recreational activities, as it is the case of the institution chosen for this research, located in Sorocaba (SP — Brazil). Through DS protocol, it was sought to analyze the users' perception of the products with respect to subjective aspects. It was also in the issues of this research, the discussion of the use of homemade adapted models within the assistive technology, called *gambiarra* in Brazil (kludge or workaround, or even a Do It Yourself product), since four of the five models tested were made this way.

KEYWORDS: *assistive technology; design; semantic differential; adaptation; disability.*

INTRODUCTION

About 15% of the world's population has some sort of disability, representing a total estimate of one billion people, according to an United Nations research.¹ The majority of this population lives in developing countries, where a considerable portion does not attend any school or paid activity. Assistive technology, more than the technical concept of physical contribution needed for the disabled, has connected its significance to the function of the social, environmental, and economic inclusion of the individual, emphasizing the need to search for changes in societies. The concept of assistive

technology can be summarized as the creation and use of devices that supplement, enhance, maintain, or give back the residual capacities of persons with disabilities, and aims at maximizing the functional performance of the individual, thus, decreasing their impossibilities (Hogetop & Santarosa, 2002). Galvão Filho and Damasceno (2008, p.4) still propose another definition, also with emphasis on the question of self-sufficiency of the individual, as follows: 'Every tool, resource or process used in order to provide greater independence and autonomy a disabled person'.²

1. Information reported on the UN website, available from: <http://www.un.org/disabilities/default.asp?id=18>. [26th November, 2013].

2. Translated by the author. Original text: 'Tecnología asistida es toda herramienta, recurso o proceso utilizado con el fin de proporcionar una mayor independencia y autonomía a la persona con discapacidad'.

The market supply reality in assistive technology is quite complex in developing countries, like Brazil, where the variety of this kind of product is scarce, and the costs are considerably high in many cases. Despite the growing development in the industrial and scientific areas, many components or even complete products are imported, increasing the final cost to the consumer. This scenario points out many needs, and among them, the need for the development of homemade products, through so-called *gambiarra*, a Brazilian word for kludge, which are specific utility improvisations involving determined contexts, such as socioeconomic factors, the use in which the industrial product is inserted, and the deconstruction of the design process to which it is related (Bonfleur, 2013). Within this context of making and/or owning adaptations, there is also the possibility to customize the product, given that most subjective and specific user requirements about artifacts are hardly attended by the industrial product, since the pleasure of using certain objects can be based on different aspects, such as functionality, innovativeness, aesthetics, personal meaning, and social values, among others (Gotszch, 2013; Tractinsky et al., 2000).

Seeking a correlation between the situations explained above, the present study sought to analyze, through the subjective usability evaluation of products called Semantic Differential (SD), five different models of an assistive technology product known as pencil grip, used by people with impaired handgrip, that requires a special ergonomic adequacy. Four of the five models used in the study were prepared in a homely way, and only one in this group was a manufactured product. The application of the DS model was carried out with the participation of professionals and patients of the chosen institution, located in Sorocaba (SP — Brazil), which offers rehabilitation activities for children and adolescents with multiple disabilities.

THE IMPORTANCE OF THIS INTERESTING OBJECT, THE PENCIL GRIP

The pencil grips are a type of assistive technology made for individuals who face some sort of restriction on the handgrip and adversities in motor coordination, which cause difficulties or impossibilities for holding objects with reduced dimensions. Individuals with Down Syndrome, some elderly people, and patients with certain types of cerebral palsy are cases that can experience this kind of difficulty, due to situations of muscle hypotonia and low motor coordination (Silva et al., 2009; Rantanen, 1999; Cruz, 2005). The pencil grip for ergonomic aid is an object made with a material of high to medium flexibility, usually in a tubular or triangular design, and with variable width (depends on the user), which fits the pencil that will be used in its interior.

It is noteworthy that the use of this type of object is not restricted only to pencils: it can be used in other artifacts that have the same or similar diameter to the hole (approximately sixty millimeters), and certain pen models, brushes, chalk waxes, and even cutlery for meals; thus being widely used in

other activities. In rehabilitation, learning, and recreational environments, such as the institution of the present study, the use of such materials has essential function to perform the tasks. One of the main activities carried out with the support of the grip in Creche Maria Claro is the artistic practices. Art and fantasy are important parts the social and subjective training of the human being (Vygostky, 1986), carrying out activities in this field and encouraging the ludic and fanciful side is extremely important for the development of children and adolescents.

In addition, when talking about models of pencil grips available in the Brazilian market of assistive technology, according to a survey conducted by the author, it was found that this type of product has a high cost. Six models of this product were found, with prices ranging from 15 to 49 Brazilian *reais*. Such costs are significantly high, considering the Brazilian social reality of most of the disabled population, which is located in the lower socioeconomic strata. This cost also justifies the low amount of products present in these types of institutions that carry out activities persons with disabilities, despite its high need. Also, it is remarkable that the cost of assistive technologies can be a restrictive factor not only in developing countries (Kolatch, 2001; Kintsch et al., 2002; Parette, 2000; Pal et al., 2011; Inge & Targett, 2005).

THE ISSUE OF KLUDGE IN A.T.

Even with the existence of federal policies to grant certain models of assistive technology in Brazil (Brasil, 1999), as well as specific lines of public and private funding (Brasil, 2004), many products of the area are not covered by such processes. The existence of these projects demonstrates the high cost related to the possession of in this assistive technology, directly related to the fact that many components of the products being commercialized are originated outside Brazil, embedding in their values the expensive costs of these proceedings of importing — and in many cases the complete artifact is imported, due to the inexistence of a national industry that works in that particular niche. Numerous initiatives that support research and practice in the area of assistive technology are currently in emergence, but they do not yet supply these latent needs, especially of lower income populations and non-governmental institutions.

Through this situation, it becomes important to discuss the artisanal adaptation of regular products in order to fulfill the specific needs of users with disabilities. This *gambiarra* (kludge or workaround) then, taken by user, by family members, or caregivers, or even by other professionals in frequent contact, such as occupational and physical therapists, usually consists of the use of abundant or available resources, with the intention to play this role of substitution in relation with the existing material human needs (Bonfleur, 2013). Such modification, generating a *Do It Yourself* (DIY) artifact, interferes promptly in the most important industrial product dimensions: form, meaning, purpose, and its material composition — then, re-designing the product (Bonfleur, 2013).

All this communicative process, accomplished through the design of the products included in the operation of adaptation, is then intermediated and resignified by the user of such products that has become an assistive to technology. According to Bonfleur (2013), the subversion of design in *gambiarra* carries implications for multiple aspects of the product and may modify it in shape, purpose, or both. Thus, this improvised product acquires new conditions to meet important aspects to the user of these technologies, such as ergonomic aspects, providing a better adjustment to the disability in question, since the skills and impairments of all people (not only the disabled) make them unique (Kintsch et al., 2002); for example, emotional, providing greater customization, with the possibility to change aspects of their original design; and of course, the economic, since the adaptation, in general, is more financially viable than buying a new artifact.

In this way, the study sought to conduct a test of assistive technology products that were manually assembled, and also of the industrialized model. Trying to show the viability of this kind of practice, with emphasis on the issue of work based on the subjective and product customization, this approach was performed through the evaluation protocol called the DS, which will be explained in the next topic.

THE MODEL OF THE SEMANTIC DIFFERENTIAL (SD)

The technique of the Semantic Differential (SD) was introduced by Osgood, Taci, and Tanenbaum in 1957, and aims at exploring the emotional, subjective, or connotative meaning of concepts used by the study object, tangent to the attitude of the users, exposing the participants to a survey composed of several bipolar descriptors, separated from each other by a seven scale table (Likert scale), demanding the users to fill it in according to their perceptions (Brandalise, 2006; Andrade, 2007; Darnell, 2006; Solórzano, 2008). The approach of the SD has its onset in studies in psychology, being grounded in behaviorist models (related to processes of encoding and decoding of the individual), space models (which makes the assumption that a concept is connected to a given space), and metric models (linked to the formation of scales for the representation and technical operational dimension of mediation between the above concept and meaning) (Andrade, 2007).

The DS is a simple, quick, and easy comprehension test, which admits variations in its application (Lanutti et al., 2013), since it allows changes on the pairs of propositions according to which most suits the case study. Due to this flexibility, the DS is used in several areas beyond the field of psychology, like, for example, in studies within the sphere of architecture (Rudy, 2005), education (Evans, 1970; Whitney & Soukup, 1988), marketing (Markechová et al., 2013), and medicine (Lopes et al., 2011). Within the scope of the present research, other researches focusing on different products are found, such as juicers (Lanutti et al., 2013), analogue desk clocks (Sevener, 2003), calculators (Solórzano, 2008), and chairs (Lin et al., 2013).

Although no specific studies on the application of DS in the area of assistive technology have been found, this technique appears to be pertinent to this type of research, due to the fact that it focuses on the subjective aspect of the design choices. Many authors call attention to the welfare, which can have a great increase when there is a concern with the appearance of these products, along with its functionality (Kintsch & De-paula, 2002; Parette & Scherer, 2004; Pullin, 2009; Norman, 2004; Desmet, 2003; Hocking, 1999), taking into account the many variables that influence this process that inhibits the stigmatization of disabled citizen, such as socio-cultural issues present in the user surroundings (Parette & Scherer, 2004). Graham Pullin (2009) also draws attention the need a change in the medicalized perspective about the products in this area, towards the adoption of a social model and with more freedom, where interventions and experimentations are enabled through design, and attending more personal perspectives (mainly subjective and emotional ones).

METHODOLOGY

This study took place within the institution located in Sorocaba (SP — Brazil). A total of eight participants joined the study: two occupational therapist professionals, and six children with an average age of 10,16 years (standard deviation: 2,67 years), with different types of grips/ pencil grips. A total of eight children that used the apparatus were detected on the institution, but only six of them were able to join the research. It sought to follow a qualitative axis of data collection, looking for the construction of an analytical framework about the products tested, emphasizing the subjective aspect of the user identification with these artifacts.

For the perceptual evaluation, five models of pencil thickener were selected. Of the five models shown, four of them were made by adaptations, inspired by the literature of the area (Bersch, 2008; Galvão Filho, 2009), and based on some models in the market. The most popular model of the industrial product in the market was the fifth model chosen. All four models were handmade by the authors, each having an average cost close to one Brazilian real, and the institution owned the fifth model used. It is noted that there was familiarity by the participants with only one of the models exposed (the industrialized model).

The models of pencil grips are the following:

Figure 01. Model A, consisting of two distinct colors of EVA (green and lilac), with dimensions of 31mm by 130mm. Built by the technique of winding EVA with adhesive tape and styrofoam glue. Source: Authors.

Figure 02. Model B, consisting of two corks, with dimensions of 35mm by 10mm, in beige color. Constructed through the use of drill machine, with drill bit of 0.03 cm and 0.07 cm. Source: Authors.

Figure 04. Model D, consisting of hard rubber with a diameter of 55mm. Source: Authors.

Figure 03. Model C, made of two different colors of EVA (green and orange) and styrofoam, with dimensions of approx. 40mm by 123mm. Built by styrofoam with triangular cut and centrally holed, shrouded by EVA on the bases and sides, with adhesive tape and styrofoam glue. Source: Authors.

Figure 05. Model E, industrialized, consisting of expanded polyethylene black, with a diameter of 25mm by 105mm long. Source: Authors.

The characteristics of each model tested were verbally explained and specified to the participants. Those specifications were also distributed on a sheet. In an individual way, the objectives of the study were explained to the members of the research, and then the Term of Free Consent and Informed (called TCLE in Brazil) was distributed to be read and understood before the signing. All of the underage participants (under eighteen years) had the documents sent to their parents or legal guardians.

It was requested that the participants (children) color drawings on A4 sheets, making use of pencil grips, using each type at a distinct time, for approximately forty minutes. The children performed the test individually, doing it one at a time, with variable intervals between them (about ten to fifty minutes). During this period, the therapists' participants remained beside the child who was testing the artefacts, questioning them about the use of the products, capturing the verbalizations, and watching them intently, with the intention of jointly filling out the questionnaire. After the test and

completion of the questionnaire, another child initiated the activity. The test occurred inside one of the rooms of the institution, with the aid of an adjustable table with height and angle adjustments.

The assessment protocol of perception used was the DS, containing twelve pairs of bipolar adjectives and descriptive situations, permeated by seven scales (ranging from -3 to 3), to be filled according to the perception of the users. The descriptions used were about the possibilities in the use of the product, permeating the functional and subjective perception of the product features. They are not presented by affinity groups in the questionnaires. It is noted that the procedure of filling the DS forms occurred jointly, by the professional helper in activities with the patient, who was properly using the object. Audio recordings with the intention of recording the utterances and spontaneous statements were also used. Direct observation of the use of the artefact, after the end of the test was also made with the intention of analyzing the more natural user interaction with the objects in question (Yin, 2003).

STAGES OF THE RESEARCH	PROCEDURES
01. Theoretical review	Review of the issues that underlie the subject of this study (TA, studies about the DS protocol, issues of improvisations and aesthetic and emotional aspects of a product)
02. Search for models on the market and homemade models	Search on the internet and in bibliographies
03. Construction of the homemade models	Acquisition and collection of materials needed for the construction of such models
04. Selection of participants	Interview and open dialogues with professionals from the institution, looking for patients who use the product
05. Product testing and implementation of the questionnaire	Presentation of the TCLE (appendix A), presentation and use of the models, by the participants, besides the filling out of the questionnaire (appendix B)
06. Analysis of results	Analysis of the data collected with the support of the previously presented theoretical review
07. Development of hypotheses	From the analysis, hypotheses were elaborated to be further investigated in conjunction with the theories studied

Table 01. Table containing the summary of the methodology used in this research.

Source: Authors.

A total of twelve hours were necessary for the conduction of this research *in loco*, with the use of a digital recorder, generating three hours recording time, and a digital camera, resulting in the photographic material of 94 JPEG files .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Five scatter plots were generated with the average of the scores given by users, each one corresponding to one type of pencil grip. In the graphs, the adjectives are grouped by

affinity, in three semantic values, as defined by Medeiros and Ashton (2006, apud Lanutti et al., 2013); ludic (attractive/repulsive; serious/fun; beautiful/ugly; common/different); practical (light/heavy; stable/unstable; comfortable/uncomfortable; sturdy/fragile); and critical (secure/insecure; easy to use/difficult to use; effective/ineffective; anatomical/anti-anatomic). The group described by the authors above as an ideological group was excluded from the evaluation charts, because of the complexity of the adjectives in accordance with this theme, since the children are the audience of this study. The charts with the results can be visualized below:

Figure 06. Graph generated from the average of the responses of the model A. Source: Authors.

Figure 07. Graph generated from the average of the responses of the model B. Source: Authors.

Figure 08. Graph generated from the average of the responses of the model C. Source: Authors.

Figure 09. Graph generated from the average of the responses of the model D. Source: Authors.

Figure 10. Graph generated from the average of the responses of the model E. Source: Authors.

Between the assignments of various topics, a large standard deviation was noted, found in all models. This situation points to an important result in the development of products in the area of assistive technology, related to the deficiencies variability. It was noticed that some models, as for example the triangular orange one, functioned in a very effective way to assist the writing of half of the participants, but was shown to be an inconvenient product to others — the members of the research, even though having the same diagnosis (cerebral palsy), have different ways of gripping, which may not fit properly to that model, as the example of refined gripping, in the form of a clamp (Paiva, 2007), practiced by a participant. Also, this indicates a possibility of including a new pair of evaluations inside the DS model in cases of A.T. products, like 'it is very specific for the disability', or 'it's not specific for the disability'. This pair could be put inside the critical affinity group, for cases when the researcher is dealing with groups without an average uniform pattern of disability. Moreover, it was perceived that, while the manufactured product used consists of a massive piece of polyethylene, disallowing major changes in its structure, the DIY artefacts allow large customizations with capacity to meet individual physical requirements via a cheap material (such as glue and adhesive tape), according to the observed.

The smallest standard deviations were found in the ludic semantic group, who were asked to answer questions regarding the aesthetic and signification aspects of the pencil grips. This demonstrates the strong relation between children and subjective issues, like shapes and colors, in products of their daily lives and, therefore, the importance of the attention to this emotional aspect during the designing of these products. The A and C models, with a composite design of colored material, and also the D model, composed of a small ball, got positive

Figure 12. Graph comparing the assessments of model C, made by the participant K, which practices immature palmar gripping (holds the material with the palm, in a sensitive manner), relative to the participant R, which has a tripod grasp (makes the use of three fingers to hold), with great force of application (Kang & Ikeuchi, 1991). Source: Authors.

reviews and reactions tangent to the visual aspects, evidencing the interest and enjoyment in their use, which may have a great collaboration in infant's educational processes (Freitas, 2007). Also, it was observed that most of the models easily found on the Brazilian market were made of dark colors, such as black (like the model used this study), and gray. Thus, this information was taken into account through the process of making DIY models for use with the protocol. Using as a reference the infantile world, grounded on these exploration ideas of colors and forms (Moura, 2006), the aspect of the handmade models quoted above were based especially on these lines. And so, the smallest differences encountered in the results on this ambit, shown before, reinforce the existence of this relation.

A peculiar situation also draws attention to this ludic side, in the case of the thickener made of a little ball. Some children played more with the object that this thickener was made from, than painted the drawing — which was not to be necessarily seen as a problem at all times, since the play helps children to relate to the world and recreate situations their daily lives, and stimulates essential actions and feelings to social life (Vygotsky, 1991). Also, according to Mafra (2007), the game within the learning process provides greater autonomy to children with disabilities, improving self-esteem and body knowledge, which increases their development.

Still exists a panorama that can be explored, derived from the results of this application. In regard to industrial products, a deeper look at the creation of a bigger affinity between user and product can take place, such as including the possibility of changing parts, formats or colors of the objects. This means that the matter of a design for few people should not be neglected in any aspect — as it actually is on many occasions — and this is imbricated this scenario as well. The collabora-

tive process also could be an important tool to improve this, once the user is one of the main potential sources of information and innovation (Gaither & Fraizer, 2002) about the product that is being developed. This collaboration can be done from the initial stages of product development, like involving the potential users and people linked to the user environment (e.g. occupational therapists, caregivers, and family) in the process, and testing prototypes using models of objective and subjective evaluation (as the DS protocol), until its post-development, (e.g. making use of an active channel of communication with the client and giving incentives for user feedbacks). *Unless the developer is a disabled person, he cannot know about being a disabled person, and so, can't develop correctly a product for us, and he has to hear us* — and this sentence, heard from a disabled citizen in a research interview, briefly summarizes this importance of capturing the user experience and personal concerns.

In general, the best scores of homemade thickeners shown by the protocol were close to the evaluations of the industrial product, showing the feasibility of using these kinds of homemade devices in teaching and recreational scenarios, always according to the specificity of disability. The possibility and adequacy to a different adaptation, both in ludic and practical issues, and its low cost of production, indicates that its use should be encouraged not only in institutions (as it is already widely practiced in Brazil), but also among family members of the children, extending the practice into different types of assistive products (once the problems related to the commercial case of pencil thickeners are similar to other types of objects found in this area — like high prices, lack of variety, and attention to personal values of the user). An example of this

idea that is already being applied there is the practice of some institutions located in the big cities of Brazil, which conduct workshops with needy families about DIY assistive products.

The protocol of the semantic differential a good response about its use in assistive technology products, but special attention must be given regarding the variables of disabilities that can be found in the application context, which can generate a very wide range of responses in the questionnaires. In the case of this present study, the data about specific physical performances related to each patient was collected from the questionnaires, with the intention of making possible the conduction of a more precise check of these pencil grip evaluations in the future. A brief summary table containing the results found by the DS model follows.

Figure 13. Participant successfully using a homemade pencil thickener model. Source: Authors.

PENCIL THICKENER	INDICATED PREHENSION	POSITIVE POINTS	CRITICAL POINTS	COSTS
	Cylindrical grasp or tripod (KANG & IKEUCHI, 1991), with more gross motor coordination.	- Use of colors; - Good ludic potential; - Softness; - Moldable thickness.	- Short durability.	Under a brazilian real.
	Cylindrical grasp or tripod grasp (KANG & IKEUCHI, 1991), with more gross motor coordination.	- Stable material.	- Not easily moldable; - Stiffness of the material; - Little ludic potential.	No cost (reused corks).
	Tripod grasp (KANG & IKEUCHI, 1991), with more gross motor coordination.	- Use of colors; - Different format; - Good ludic potential; - Moldable thickness.	- Weakness of the inner material (styrofoam);	Under a brazilian real.
	Spherical grasp (KANG & IKEUCHI, 1991), brush grasp or jaw chuck (BERRY, 1999)	- Different format; - Good ludic potential;	- Heavy; - Little possibility of customization; - Instability; - Requires practice for better handling.	About two brazilian reais.
	Cylindrical grasp or tripod grasp (KANG & IKEUCHI, 1991), with more gross motor coordination.	- Stable material; - Softness.	- Heavy; - Little ludic potential; - Little possibility of customization.	About 25 brazilian reais.

Table 02. Table containing the results found by the DS protocol.

Source: Authors.

CONCLUSION

The so called *gambiarra* has a special social role in assistive technology, and even with the pejorative baggage charged by the term, in this area it is maybe a solution which is often the only affordable means of owning certain devices, in some socioeconomic contexts. In this study, the pencil grip reviews have proved the useful potential of this artifact, as an aid mechanism for the implementation of tasks, in certain cases (depending on the model and disability), with the same performance of the manufactured product, within the terms evaluated by protocol. Thus, these improvised products have the capacity to meet the everyday user's needs of this type of artefact, added to the personal and subjective value that this homemade product can bring, working the design for the emotional side of the user, and more to it: a fact of great importance, especially in view of the child user, and the fact that this facet is often denied by commercial models.

Through this complex framework, the DS evaluation model becomes a functional protocol for this kind of test, being agile and quick, capturing the most instant facets of use of a product. Promoting the view of the most subjective characteristics, this model allowed the research to notice the importance of the most ludic features of the product design used in the infant learning environment in the area of assistive technology, creating a greater affinity between the user's universe and the product, commonly not provided by most popular models in the market. Still, even with the limitations of the test due to the multiplicity of physical profiles of the study participants, it was possible through this research to achieve a visualization of this aspect linked to the emotional factor, which is very important and attached to the infant sphere.

Finally, it is expected that this research can collaborate somehow on future studies concerned with the subjective side of assistive technology in all of your means of development, whether through a DIY method, or by mass production. The opportunity of seeing and adding a personal value on these type of products is narrowly linked with wellbeing and the quality of performing daily activities. And it can be observed and improved through lots of different ways; for instance, by using evaluating methods as the DS protocol, via the collaboration of professionals immersed in the universe of the user, or by tacit acknowledgments, like the living experiences of all social actors involved in this process.

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APPENDIX A

UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DE SÃO CARLOS (UFSCar)
 CAMPUS SOROCABA
 PROGRAMA DE PÓS-GRADUAÇÃO EM ENGENHARIA DE PRODUÇÃO

Avaliação de percepção de produto

Nome do(a) profissional: _____ Idade: _____
 Nome do(a) paciente: _____ Idade: _____
 Deficiência: _____

Modelo: (A) (B) (C) (D) (E)

	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	
É leve								É pesado
É estável								É instável
É comum								É diferente
É confortável								É incômodo
É seguro								É inseguro
É resistente								É frágil
É atrativo								É repulsivo
É sério								É divertido
É de uso fácil								É de uso complicado
É eficaz								É ineficaz
É bonito								É feio
É anatômico								Não é anatômico

TERMO DE CONSENTIMENTO LIVRE E ESCLARECIDO (TCLE)

Convidamos o (a) senhor(a) para participar da pesquisa **Noções perceptivas de modelos de engrossadores de lápis, através do protocolo de avaliação DS**, sob a responsabilidade da pesquisadora **Juliana Maria Moreira Soares**, a qual pretende avaliar diversos modelos de engrossadores de lápis, de acordo com suas diversas características.

Sua participação é voluntária e se dará por meio do **preenchimento de um questionário mediante o uso dos diferentes modelos de engrossadores de lápis.**

A participação nessa pesquisa não apresenta riscos físicos ou psicológicos ao participante. Aceitando participar dessa pesquisa, **estará contribuindo para os estudos no campo de tecnologia assistiva com relação à sua construção caseira e seus aspectos subjetivos com relação ao usuário.**

Se depois de consentir em sua participação o senhor (a) desistir de continuar participando, tem o direito e a liberdade de retirar seu consentimento em qualquer fase da pesquisa, seja antes ou depois da coleta dos dados, independente do motivo e sem nenhum prejuízo a sua pessoa. O (a) senhor (a) não terá nenhuma despesa e também não receberá nenhuma remuneração.

Os resultados da pesquisa serão analisados e publicados, mas sua identidade não será divulgada, sendo guardada em sigilo. Para qualquer outra informação, o (a) senhor (a) poderá entrar em contato com o pesquisador no endereço **Rua Ana Augusto, 470, ap. 101, Sorocaba – SP**, ou pelo telefone **(12) 99106 0497**.

Eu, _____, fui informado (a) sobre o que o pesquisador quer fazer e porque precisa da minha colaboração, e entendi a explicação. Por isso, eu concordo em participar do projeto, sabendo que não vou ganhar nada e que posso sair quando quiser. Este documento é emitido em duas vias que serão ambas assinadas por mim e pelo pesquisador, ficando uma via com cada um de nós.

Sorocaba, _____ de _____ de 2014

Assinatura do participante

Assinatura do Pesquisador Responsável